

MUSIC THERAPY IN PEOPLE WITH SCHIZOPHRENIA: SCOPING REVIEW

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Abstract

Introduction : According to the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that around the world there are 379 million people with mental disorders, with 20 million people affected by schizophrenia and psychosis. Hallucinations are divided into 5 types, namely auditory, visual, taste, touch and inhalation hallucinations. Hallucination disorders can be treated with pharmacological and non-pharmacological therapy. Non-pharmacological therapy is safer to use because it does not cause side effects like drugs. Music therapy is one therapy that is often used for auditory hallucinations **Aim**: The aim of this research is to determine music therapy for people with Schizophrenia **Method**: The approach used in this literature study is a scoping review. The search for articles in this literature study used 3 database sources, namely PubMed, Ebscohost, and Google Scholar. The keywords used in this literature study use Boolean operators, namely "Schizophrenia OR Schizophrenia" AND "music therapy OR music intervention" for searching articles in English, as well as "Skizofrenia" AND "terapi musik" to search for articles in Indonesian. **Result** : Search results using these keywords yielded 250 articles and only 6 articles were reviewed and analyzed in this literature study. **Conclusion**: From the six articles, music therapy combined with the administration of psychotropic drugs can provide benefits for reducing the level of auditory hallucinations in schizophrenia sufferers, either with music that has a soft rhythm or using music that is popular.

Keywords: Schizophrenia, Music Therapy, Music Intervention.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Mental Health Report (2022) estimates that around the world there are 379 million people with mental disorders, with 24 million people affected by schizophrenia and psychosis (Organization, 2022). Data from the 2018 Basic Needs Research Results (Riskesmas) shows that the proportion of households with schizophrenic psychosis in Indonesia is 282,654 people and 43,890 people are in East Java (Riskesmas, 2018) .

The World Mental Health Report (2022) stated that mental health is when a person is in good health and can feel happiness and is able to face life's challenges, has a positive attitude towards himself and others, and can accept others as they should be. Apart from that, it is said that mental health is where the condition of an individual develops physically, mentally, spiritually and socially so that he is aware of his own abilities, able to cope with pressure, work productively and contribute to his community, but if the condition of the individual's development is not appropriate it is called a disorder (Organization, 2022).

Hallucinations are one of the symptoms of sensory perception disorders experienced by people with mental disorders (Shao et al., 2021). Hallucinations are false perceptual distortions that occur due to maladaptive neurobiological responses, sufferers actually experience sensory distortions as real things and respond to them. (Silverstein & Lai, 2021). Hallucinations are divided into 5 types, namely auditory, visual, taste, touch and inhalation hallucinations. (Moritz et al., 2024). Auditory hallucinations are hallucinations that are often experienced by people with mental

disorders, for example hearing the sound of something screeching, swishing, noise, and in the form of words or sentences. Individuals occur to them, so that sufferers are often seen arguing or talking to themselves in the voices they hear (Romeo & Spironelli, 2022). Hallucination disorders can be treated with pharmacological and non-pharmacological therapy. Non-pharmacological therapy is safer to use because it does not cause side effects like drugs.

2. METHODOLOGY

The approach used in this literature study is a scoping review. Scoping review is a method used to identify literature in depth and comprehensively which is obtained from various sources with various research methods and has a relationship or relevance to the research topic. (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005 dalam Widiasih et al., 2020). The purpose of a scoping review is to answer questions from research topics that have been determined using various sources of similar research articles, then group them and draw conclusions. (Widiasih et al., 2020).

The search for articles in this literature study used 3 database sources, namely PubMed, Ebscohost, and Google Scholar using predetermined keywords. Keywords must be defined comprehensively to select appropriate articles and eliminate irrelevant articles. The keywords used in this literature study use Boolean operators, namely "Schizophrenia OR Schizophrenia" AND "music therapy OR music intervention" AND "hallucinations OR voices OR auditory hallucination" for searching articles in English, as well as "Skizofrenia" AND "terapi musik" AND "halusinasi" to search for articles in Indonesian.

Selection criteria are carried out by determining inclusion criteria to help find appropriate literature. Inclusion criteria can determine the underlying factors the review will look for. The inclusion criteria applied to this literature study are articles discussing music therapy interventions for schizophrenia sufferers, the year the article was published in the last 10 years (2014-2024), articles using Indonesian or English, type of RCT or quasi-experimental study, as well as articles full text.

After searching for articles through several databases, 250 articles were found which were then sorted. Sorting is carried out with the aim of obtaining articles that are appropriate to the topic of the literature study being carried out. Articles that have been found through the database are then sorted using inclusion criteria. After sorting, 6 articles were analyzed. Below is the article sorting process carried out to obtain articles that are appropriate to the literature study topic.

Figure 1.. Diagram PRISMA Flowchart

3. RESULT

There are several descriptions related to music therapy for schizophrenia sufferers. This literature study consists of 6 articles which collectively explain the benefits of music therapy for patients with schizophrenia. Search results using these keywords yielded 250 articles and only 6 articles were reviewed and analyzed in this literature study. The articles obtained are displayed in Indonesian and English. There are 4 articles with RCT research type and 2 other articles are quasi experimental. Of the 6 articles, research was conducted in 4 countries, 2 studies were conducted in Turkey, 2 studies were conducted in Indonesia, 1 study was conducted in Taiwan, and 1 study was conducted in Denmark. To see the specific results of the article analysis, see table 1.

Table 1. Articles Related to Music Therapy for People with Schizophrenia

No	Author and year of publication	Title	Purpose	Population and Sample	Method	Intervention	Result
1	Zincir, Zincir, Yenel, Kivilcim, Cetin, Tulay, Semiz (2014)	Classical Turkish Music as Group Music Therapy for Inpatients with Schizophrenia: Feasibility and Efficacy	The aim of this study was to examine the feasibility and efficacy of Turkish classical music therapy as group music therapy for patients diagnosed with schizophrenia	The population in this study was 107 female patients treated at the Women's Mental Health Service of the Erenkoy Research and Training Hospital, and the sample was 85 patients who were divided into 2 groups: 1. Intervention group (n=45) 2. Control group (n=40)	RCT	Samples included in the study group will receive music therapy for 12 sessions in 4 weeks, with each session lasting approximately 50-55 minutes. Evaluations are carried out on both groups every week	From this research it was found that there was a significant reduction in the severity of symptoms and an increase in the ability to adapt to the social environment in the therapy group compared to the control group.
2	Rafina Damayanti, Jumaini, Sri Utami (2014)	The Effectiveness of Classical Music Therapy on Reducing the Level of Auditory Hallucinations in Patients with Auditory Hallucinations at	To determine the effectiveness of classical music therapy on reducing the level of hallucinations in children patients with auditory hallucinations at RSJ Tampan, Riau Province	A sample of 34 people was divided into 2 groups, namely the experimental group with 17 people and the control group with 17 people.	Quasi-experimental	In the experimental group, music therapy was conducted daily for 5 days, with a duration of 10-15 minutes each day.	From the research, it was found that in the control group, there was no change in the level of hallucinations from pretest to posttest, in contrast to the experimental group,

No	Author and year of publication	Title	Purpose	Population and Sample	Method	Intervention	Result
		RSJ Tampan, Riau Province					which showed a change in the level of hallucinations from a score of 3 to 2.
3	Yanti, Sitepu, Sitepu, Pitriani, Purba (2020)	The Effectiveness of Music Therapy on Reducing the Level of Auditory Hallucinations in Psychiatric Patients at the Psychiatric Hospital Prof. Dr. M. Ildrem	This study aims to determine the effectiveness of classical music therapy in reducing the level of hallucinations in patients with auditory hallucinations.	The sample in the study consisted of 22 people.	Quasi eksperimental	22 sample individuals received music therapy for 7 days every morning and evening. The treatment ended on the 7th day, and auditory hallucinations were re-observed.	From this study, it was found that there is an effect before and after the music therapy intervention on the reduction of auditory hallucination levels (p=0.000), with an average score before therapy of 4.32 becoming 1.68 after therapy.
4	Yi-Nuo Shiha,b, Chi-Sheng Chenc, Hsin-Yu Chianga and Chien-Hsiou Liua (2015)	Influence of background music on work attention in clients with chronic schizophrenia	Based on occupational therapy theory, environmental sounds, colors, and decorations can affect individual performance, this study studying the influence of music on work attention in people with schizophrenia.	SampleIn this study, there were 49 participants.	RCT	This intervention shows significant variance (sig = 0.071). For Group 3 (popular music), the intervention has a significant variance (sig = 0.048).	This research shows that background music can improve the attention performance of people with chronic schizophrenia. Further research is needed with a larger sample size to support the

No	Author and year of publication	Title	Purpose	Population and Sample	Method	Intervention	Result
							study's findings.
5	Inge Nygaard Pedersen et al (2021)	Music Therapy vs. Music Listening for Negative Symptoms in Schizophrenia: Randomized, Controlled, Assessor- and Patient-Blinded Trial	To determine the efficacy of music therapy for negative symptoms in patients with schizophrenia.	The sample for this research consists of 57 participants.	RCT	This intervention showed a significant decrease from baseline to 25 weeks on the PANSS negative subscale. In the secondary outcomes, there were no differences between the groups observed in The Brief Negative Symptom Scale, WHOQOL-Bref (Quality of Life), The Helping Alliance Questionnaire, and The Global Assessment of Functioning in the intention to treat or complete the population using the Mixed Effects Model.	From this study, the main result is the reduction of negative symptoms measured by the total score of the negative subscale. Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), assessed by blinded raters, using mixed-effects model analysis.
6	Sükran Ertekin Pinar RN, PhD & Havva Tel, RN, PhD (2019)	The Effect of Music on Auditory Hallucination and Quality of Life in Schizophrenia	To determine the effect of music on auditory hallucinations and quality of life of patients with	The sample consists of 28 patients divided into 2 groups.	Randomized controlled trial	Both groups were evaluated after six months using: 1. Scale for the assessment	In this study, it was found that in the intervention group, there was a decrease in positive

No	Author and year of publication	Title	Purpose	Population and Sample	Method	Intervention	Result
		enic Patients: A Randomized Controlled Trial	schizophrenia			nt of positive symptoms (SAPS) 2. The characteristics of auditory hallucinations questionnaire 3. The World Health Organization Quality of Life Scale Control group Standard care, without music Intervention Group Standard care, plus listening to music with a rost tone through an MP3 Player using headphones for 15 minutes.	symptoms and an improvement in quality of life by the sixth month.

4. DISCUSSION

This literature review examines the advantages of music therapy for schizophrenia patients experiencing auditory hallucinations. Music is an artistic medium that conveys emotions and ideas through its auditory elements. Music offers numerous advantages, including alleviating stress, anxiety, and mental strain. Hallucinations are positive symptoms of schizophrenia that induce perceptual distortions, which may be aural, visual, or tactile in nature. Auditory hallucinations are perceptual anomalies in individuals that lead them to perceive noises that are only audible to them. These sounds might be highly unsettling for patients in the conquering phase.

Music therapy is a form of psychosocial rehabilitation that utilizes music to achieve positive results when combined with pharmacological therapy. Music therapy has the potential to enhance concentration, restore self-confidence, improve social relationships, and increase self-esteem. The music utilized in the six articles reviewed encompasses classical music, rast music, popular music, and traditional Turkish music. Classical music, which originated in the western region, is characterized by a gentle tone that can induce a sense of tranquility. Rost music is a rhythm that

is used to recite the Quran in a soft and rapid manner. The client may be distracted from the hallucinations they are experiencing by the music they are listening to.

The research entitled "Classical Turkish Music as Group Music Therapy for Inpatients with Schizophrenia: Feasibility and Efficacy" involved music therapy utilizing traditional Turkish music for 50-55 minutes every session over a duration of 4 weeks. The findings indicated a notable decrease in symptom severity and an enhancement in social adaptability within the therapy group relative to the control group. This study utilized tambourines as the primary instrument, while participants engaged with many additional instruments, including tambours, zithers, tiny drums, and kemanchas, in group settings. (Zincir, Zincir, Yenel, Kivilcim, Cetin, Tulay, Semiz, 2014)

Furthermore, a separate trial in Indonesia revealed a reduction in hallucination levels following the administration of music therapy for 10-15 minutes each morning, afternoon, and evening. The clients will collectively listen to classical music transmitted via speakers. The application of Röst music involves listening to MP3 recordings for 15 minutes whenever the patient experiences auditory hallucinations, and this practice continues when the client is at home. Yanti, Sitepu, Sitepu, Pitriani, Purba (2020). The intervention group exhibited a reduction in positive symptoms and an enhancement in quality of life by the sixth month.

5. CONCLUSION

The six publications indicate that music therapy, in conjunction with psychotropic medication, can effectively diminish auditory hallucinations in people with schizophrenia, utilizing either soothing rhythms or preferred musical selections. Moreover, both listening to and performing music collaboratively can enhance social ties among patients experiencing auditory hallucinations.

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